

FOUNDATIONAL LITERACY AND NUMERACY AMONGST SCHOOL CHILDREN-A STATUS STUDY IN UDUPI DISTRICT-KARNATAKA.

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ABSTRACT

The importance of education need not be over emphasised. However, the basic principles of school education or primary education are to make children read, write in a given language apart from skills connected with numerical. These basic skills are called Functional Literacy and Numeracy skills.

Under the given general teaching and learning situation, children are expected to acquire certain level of literacy and numeracy skills. For various reasons, the children may not acquire the expected level of literacy and numeracy. If the child is physically or mentally disabled, then the child's FLN level will be below the expected level. The other reasons for deficient learning could be irregular attendance of the child(migrants), language problem, illiterate parents, paucity of teachers, defective school environment, drop-outs etc.

State-wise/district-wise surveys by organizations such as Pratham conducted over a period of 15 years (ASER) very clearly indicated the the level of FLN amongst primary school children. The Survey has painted a very grim picture in most States including Karnataka. The Department of Education, Government of Karnataka, through various tools has identified the anomalies in school education in the context of FLN.

The District Institute of Education and Training (DIET), Udupi, along with the Department of Education, Udupi have tried to tackle the problem on a 'Mission Mode' (FLN Abhiyan). The school education functionaries (CRPs,BRPs, Assistant Directors, BEOs, Faculty members–DIET, teachers) were all involved in this month-long Abhiyan.

Training Programmes were held for the teachers at various education blocks of the district with the help of resource persons to make teachers understand the problem better and to use strategies to reduce FLN deficient children in their schools.

To enthuse teachers/schools, it was suggested that best performing schools under FLN Abhiyan will be evaluated by a Team and certificates given. (awarded)

Apart from the DIET team studying the progress of schools, an independent evaluation of the Abhiyan was undertaken by a consultant. Around 100 schools (government, aided and private) were selected on convenient sampling method from all the education blocks in the district. A structured questionnaire, was designed incorporating some important issues of FLN and was administered to headmasters/other teachers.

Data/information thus collected was analysed and observations presented. Observations of the evaluation has certain 'policy implications'.

Keywords: Literacy, Numeracy, Abhiyan, Physical and mental disability, DIET, CRP, BRP, BEO, ASER.

INTRODUCTION:

The importance of literacy and education need not be overemphasised. One of the important indices of human development is 'Education'; the others being, income, health etc. Those of the nations which have very good education, income and longevity of life are ranked top ones in Human Development across nations. The advantages of being educated are very many. Education, thus is inextricably interwoven with the individual as well as national development.

In India, imparting education and make people literate has been a great challenge. In such a vast country with innumerable spoken languages, economic and socio-cultural disparities, it was not easy to impart required quality education to the people, mainly children. With the limited resources, country had to decide very deligently as to whether the country had to achieve the mandated objectives of 'universal education' envisaged in the country or expand higher education. All the Committees and Commissions have written about the neglect of the country with elementary education, giving more importance for higher education

This neglect on various issues got manifested in to problems of serious nature, one such problem is the issue connected with 'Foundational Literacy and Numeracy (FLN)' amongst elementary school children. The problem is that children are not in a position learn and reach the required level of competency especially they do not possess the functional reading, writing and numeracy skills. The reasons for this inability of children to exhibit required skill level are very many.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

As per the Forty Second Amendment to the Constitution of India (1976), education is made a state subject (concurrent), giving powers to states to manage this vast sector which deals with 'human resource'.

Within the state, the district is the most important administrative unit for education. In the State of Karnataka,

Deputy Director Public Instruction(DDPI) is the district educational head, who is supported by Block Education Officers at education blocks, having Block Resource (BRP) and Cluster Resource Persons (CRP), down the line.

Schools are managed by Head Masters/Mistres assisted by teachers. Schools have School Development and Monitoring Committees(SDMC) having parents as members apart from others. Private schools have Management Committees. There are different types of schools (public, private-aided, private-unaided, KPS, CBSE, ICSE etc.).

All the schools have children who are not in the main stream of learning and they suffer out of learning disability.

During 80s, a holistic approach in primary education was replaced by the existing sectoral narrow approach. Important issues highlighted included the following:

1. a. Access to primary education to all children up to 14 years' age.
- b. Universal participation through formal or non-formal mode of education
- c. Universal achievement of at least minimum level of education.
2. Foundational literacy in which the self-reliance in the 3Rs along with relevant education relating to the needs of the individual, family and community.
3. Special emphasis on women's education and development.
4. Post-literacy continuing education and inculcation of basic skills for survival and general well-being.

National Policy on Education-1986 emphasises highest priority to solve 'problem of children drop-out' and the school shall adopt meticulously planned strategies to ensure retention of children in schools.

Stress on equalisation of educational benefits for SCs, STs, backwards and minorities, women, those from border and desert zones etc. continued.

National Literacy Campaign was different from the earlier ones as attention was given to the level of learning.

Operation Black board started in 1987-88 insisted that the school building should comprise of atleast 2 large rooms with a verandha with toilets for boys and girls separately; atleast two teachers in each school, preferably one lady; provision of essential teaching /learning materials including blackboards, charts, maps, toys and equipment for work experience. The idea was to reduce distance between concept and reality.

United Nations declared the year 1990 as 'International Literacy Year' and a World Conference on 'Education for All by 2000' was held at Bangkok. These events provided impetus to India and a large number of activities to reach the set target of Educaion for All by 2000 were conceived and implemented.

During 1990s, Ernakulam district of Kerala became fully literate, followed by Burdwan and Bankura of West Bengal, Dakshina Kannada of Karnataka, Sindhudurg and Wardha of Maharashtra, Union Territory of Pandicherry and Narasimhapur district of Madhya Pradesh.

As per the recommendations of National Policy on Education-1988, Mahila Samakhya was launched which was entrusted the work of up-liftment of women including literacy and education of women apart from others.

Innovative education projects such as 'Bihar Education Project', Rajasthan's 'LokaJambish', Uttara Pradesh's 'Education for All' were on the anvil and served as examples of good models which could be emulated.

Thus, during the post-independent era, efforts were on to make country literate and to harvest the dividends of democracy.

Despite all the efforts, the sector suffers out of certain serious problems-one such problem being children at the elementary level not reaching desired level of learning, especially the challenge connected with functional Foundational literacy and numeracy. This problem is experienced by most schools across the country.

However, a scientific and systematic study of FLN was undertaken by a Delhi based NGO-Pratham in 2004 in 19 districts of 17 states across India. This survey is called Annual Status of Education Report (ASER). In the very first report Pratham reported that, in the surveyed districts percentage of children enrolled in schools was very high (85-90%+), especially in 6-10 age group. But in many states, 50% children in std.2 and above, going to government schools, could not read even simple sentences. 60% children could not do simple subtraction, leave alone multiplication and division. For the first time, a number was put to 'status of basic learning in the country'. ASER- an annual exercise, which was planned to go up to December-2010, continued for 15 years creating a very useful databank on FLN in all the states and districts of India, deploying a very huge trained manpower drawn from various organisations.

Subsequent to Pratham, various other bodies have been working on the issue of FLN in various states, districts including all districts of Karnataka. In the State of Karnataka, State Annual Education Survey are done as National Education Surveys. All these surveys give a dismal picture of a percentage of children unable to be with others with regard to the level of learning.

The State Annual Report on Education 2024(Karnataka) reports that 7% of children studying in 3rd standard could not read even a single alphabet and a very small percentage children are in a position to do addition, subtraction, multiplication and division.

The World Bank Report about India observes that- in India children are coming to schools but the country has failed to involve these children in the process of learning. India is listed second amongst those 12 nations where children in 2nd standard could not read their own mother tongue.

As per the National Achievement Survey, 59% children in the country could not read, write and understand things at the minimum level. 54% children could not read or write a single word in English.

As per the NCERT Report, 81% children suffer out of examination phobia. In the country 8% children are mentally challenged.

Experts opine that required reforms should start from the elementary level itself.

Reading materials(books) are to be written keeping 'knowledge building process' in view. Through activities the child should learn and broaden his vision of the world. Various subjects are to be taught depending upon the capacity of the child. Teacher's trainings are to be given priority. (Ramakrishna Bhat Chokkady-2025)

Scientists, medical professionals observe that the growth of child's brain starts in the mother's womb. The evolution of child's brain is maximum up to 5-6 years of age. The brain controls all the parts of the body. Brain controls behaviour and emotions, learning and remembering, sleep and dream, breathing, talking and listening and controls heartbeat. Brain is responsible for scientific thinking, interest in music, literature, art forms etc. Thus, the brain holds key for almost every activity in humans (Srinivas Bharath M.M.,2022).

REASONS FOR LEARNING DISABILITY AMONGST CHILDREN:

Though the child's brain is a very creative apparatus, during schooling, it may not acquire required competencies in reading, writing and numerical. Such skills may be less amongst FLN challenged children compared to the normal children.

The reasons for such deficiencies are many. Few important reasons could be as hereunder:

Continuous absence from the school as in children of migrant labourers (Krishna Kothai, Ashoka Kamath,2024)

Illiterate parents who do not realise the importance of literacy and education; hence cannot guide their children.

Accessibility to school.

Inadequate qualified teachers.

School environment which is not conducive for learning.

Mental/physical disability of children.

Various other child specific/school specific/area specific problems.

FOUNDATIONAL LITERACY AND NUMERACY 'ABHIYAN' IN UDUPI DISTRICT-KARNATAKA.

Udupi district is one of the progressive, Coastal districts of the State of Karnataka. In literacy and education, the district stands out. In early 90s, the district (earstwhile Dakshina Kanada) declared itself as totally literate, next to Ernakulam in Kerala. Human Development Report of Udupi District-2008 and subsequent such Reports give details of achievements /accomplishments of the district at length. (Udupi District Human Development Report-2008). Education of women in the district is very high and is quite above the national average. Owing to quality education that is imparted, district attracts a large number of students from other

districts. Despite its reputation in the field of education and literacy, the district has very many problems to be addressed-one such problem is the issue connected with FLN of children.

SOME STATISTICS PERTAINING TO ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN UDUPI DISTRICT:

TABLE-1

Enrollment of students to schools during 2024-2025

Lower and Higher Elementary Schools run by the Department of Education

Primary Schools run by the Department of Social Welfare

NavodayaVidyalaya Schools

KendriyaVidyalaya Schools

Private Aided Primary Schools

Private Unaided Primary Schools

TOTAL ENROLLMENT OF STUDENTS IN THE ABOVE SIX GROUP OF SCHOOLS, CLASS-WISE

Class 1	Class 2	Class 3	Class 4	Class 5	Class 6	Class 7	Total
13,995	14,225	14,364	16,665	16,224	17,097	16,557	1,09,127

(Source: DISE through DIET, Udupi)

TABLE-2

BLOCK-WISE DISTRIBUTION OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN UDUPI DISTRICT(2024-2025)

TOTAL NUMBER OF PRIMARY SCHOOLS				
BLOCK	Govt		Aided	Unaided
	LPS	HPS		
Bramhavara	27	60	41	33
Byndoor	81	95	6	25
Karkala	44	82	26	37
Kundapura	45	75	15	30
Udupi	5	45	45	61
Total	202	357	133	186

(Source: DISE through DIET, Udupi)

District Institute of Education and Trainig (DIET), Udupi, along with he Education department/ structured an FLN redressal activity in a ‘Mission mode’(Abhiyan), involving all the teachers and education administrators of the district.

STRUCTURE OF THE FLN MISSION:

The following steps were observed:

Intimation to all lower and higher elementary schools about the FLN Mission.

One district level Trainer's training was conducted to resource persons who in turn would conduct trainings for teachers at various education blocks. In identified schools of blocks, trainings were conducted to school teachers.

The suggested activities of FLN Mission were to be completed in one month (which was extended by one more month)- during November/December-2023.

Schools were to 'self-evaluate' their activities of FLN Abhiyan, including the outcome and send the report to DIET.

An expert team visited schools, evaluated FLN activities/outcome during the Mission month and gave final results

The identified schools were given certificates in a district level function organised at the Zilla Panchayat, attended by various officials (District Commissioner, Chief Executive Officer, DDPI, Principal-DIET and others).

TRAINING PROGRAMMES:

The training programmes for master resource persons and teachers were well planned and executed.

Training programmes had five sessions with a short inaugural programme.

In the first session the importance of literacy and education were highlighted, listing important impediments including children not learning adequately whereby falling out of mainstream. The process of learning and teaching were dealt upon.

The issue of inability of children to reach the expected level was discussed. The intensity of the problem, mainly at the elementary level was discussed quoting surveys such as ASER (Pratham), National Annual Education Survey, State Annual Education Survey etc. While discussing various other issues connected with FLN, the correct way of teaching languages and numeracy was touched upon. The need and importance of the proposed FLN Abhiyan was explained and various steps involved and the time schedule were driven home.

Expert resource persons handled sessions on languages (Kannada, English)- the methodology of teaching, the probable problems-how to overcome them etc. This was followed by a session on teaching numerics and various nuances connected with it. It was observed that such sessions are to be made interesting and how to make them interesting.

This model training package was replicated at various education blocks which were attended by the identified teachers of different elementary schools.

It was communicated to schools that the whole Abhiyan is 'zero budgeted'.

There was an activity based teaching session where through interesting activities children are made to learn. Such activities were demonstrated by the resource person.

These training programmes were repeated by the trained master resource persons in 20 hoblis of the education blocks of the district for teachers drawn from the concerned hobli/block.

INDEPENDENT EVALUATION BY A EXPERT RESEARCHER:

DIET, Udupi, identified a researcher to independently evaluate the results of the FLN Mission 'Activities and its Outcome'.

The identified evaluator had attended the Trainer's Training and other few block level trainings.

OBJECTIVES OF THE EVALUATION:

To record the intensity of student s who are not in the mainstream of learning.

Mainly to observe the various FLN activities that schools are taking up.

To understand and report the methods schools are following in reducing the problem/s connected with FLN.

To know asto whether schools are following the FLN instructions given by DIET.

To discuss with the teachers and know the reasaons for learning disability in their schools.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Around 100 schools were visited with the convenient sampling method. Schools were selected from all the education blocks of Udupi District-Udupi, Brahmavara, Karkala, Kundapura and Byndoor. & 0% schools belonged to government; 30% were aided private and unaided private schools

A questionnaire, keeping the objectives of the study was designed to collect information.

Though majority of schools visited were government schools, aided and unaided schools were also visited.

The Head Masters of the school along with those teachers who had attended FLN Training were interviewed.

FIELD OBSERVATIONS:

Schools (lower and higher primary) where student strength was very small, the problem of FLN could not be traced as the students were not there (around 10%).

In majority of government schools and few aided private schools teachers knew about FLN and related problems. Around 5% of private schools had no idea about FLN.

Amongst schools visited, almost all government schools had made lists of children who are FLN challenged.

In almost all the schools where school representatives attended Training, it was reported that they had teacher's meeting later to discuss about the issue of FLN. However, this was not true with most private-unaided schools and few aided private schools.

A small number of government schools visited reported that they had conducted parent's meeting as a part of the Abhiyan; other government schools reported that they had informed the parents about FLN on an earlier occasion. Private schools did not go for parent's meeting as a part of the FLN Mission.

As a part of the FLN Mission, schools were expected to circulate messages from dignitaries which was not done by any school visited (0%).

Almost all the government schools and few aided private schools had made class-wise FLN challenged students and teachers could give details clearly.

Around 50% of schools had maintained separate registers about the students who needed special attention and care.

All the government schools and few other schools had 'print rich environment'. The walls were painted with pictorial information on various topics which would assist children to learn and retrieve.

Majority of the schools visited had library facility which was being used in different ways. Few schools reported that books are issued to children to read and return. Few others opined that they have a library hour during which time students read books of their choice. Few schools had 'library corner' which was being used (not many).

In all most all the government schools visited, respondent teachers observed that activities as per 'Oodu Karnataka'. This was not true with private aided and unaided schools where such material was not supplied by the government (Department of Education). This was true with the use of 'maths kits'.

Creation of 'learning corners' as per 'Vidya Pravesh Hand Book' was a positive aspect in few government schools.

Activity based learning was being followed in all most all the schools visited, the intensity of which varied from school to school. Few government schools did extremely well in this area.

But for those schools where student strength is abysmally low, in rest of the schools visited hand written posters, writings etc by students were encouraged. In few schools visited compilation of such writings on monthly/annual basis was observed to be practiced. Such annual volumes were kept in the library.

With regard to the special activities taken up by the schools with regard to the issue of FLN, schools were at various levels.

- a. Some of the private unaided schools visited were observed to have done nothing, one school (1%) was totally unaware of the concept of FLN; few aided schools also did not take the exercise seriously.
- b. Majority of the government schools took up the Mission instruction seriously and adopted different methods such as the following:

FLN challenged students were given special attention- In few schools such students were given additional coaching either in the morning before regular classes commence or during the lunch interval, few schools allotted evening time.

In those schools (KPS) where the student strength is huge and so are students who are not in the main stream, different teachers took different subjects in groups and gave required coaching.

In majority of the schools visited, where the number of children with learning disability is less, students were given special attention during the regular hours of teaching. Attaching a normal student with learning disabled ones was (buddy pairing)

DURING DISCUSSION WITH SCHOOL TEACHERS, THE FOLLOWING PROBLEMS CAME TO FORE:

Those schools where migrant children are more, the number of children with FLN difficiency is more as these students absent themselves to schools for a very long duration, hence fall out of lewarning track.

Few schools had mentally/physically challenged children who find it difficult to learn.

Schools which are in small towns find it difficult to retain challenged children late after school hours, as they have to board vehicles immediately after school hours (auto, school bus, van etc) Eg. Places such as Katapady, Padubidri, Brahmavara, Karkala, Kundapura etc. The vehicle comes at the time of school beginning.

In many of the government schools, the number of teachers is less than the required number; teachers are over burdened with other works and they are not in a position to concentrate on remedial teaching.

In general, it was observed that in government schools FLN issue was given more importance than private ones. There were a couple of aided private schools which took interest in the activities of the Abhiyan.

GENERAL OBSERVATIONS:

It was very clear from the study that all most all the teachers are aware of the problem connected with the deficient learning levels of children in their schools and the immediate need of bringing these children to main stream. They are aware of remedial teaching. What is lacking is some concrete action at the school level.

In this context, the FLN Abhiyan which the department (DIET) has Abhiyan has alerted the teachers conceived and executed was a very good move in the direction of reducing the intensity of the problem, though not completely eliminate it. The output of the Mission FLN has been very satisfactory. It has alerted the teachers and put them in to action in their busy schedule of activities.

Self-evaluation, assessment by an expert team for identifying good work and recognising schools for their good performance was indeed an act of appreciation which would motivate teachers/schools to intensify their work in the coming years.

The training imparted at various levels was very meaningful and useful. The officials of the Education department including DIET have taken the exercise very seriously and executed the Abhiyan very successfully.

SUGGESTIONS:

In the backdrop of the field study and discussions with various stakeholders, the following suggestions may be considered.

The learnings from the Mission FLN, should get transformed in to the institutional mode.

Activities suggested and learnt, should be used from the beginning of the school academic year. For example, the learning deficiency amongst children are to be identified in the beginning of the year and those children are to be continuously supervised till they are in the mainstream.

The department has to train teachers as has been done during the Mission.

Officials (CRPs, BRPs, BEOs) have to supervise this FLN activity regularly.

Review of the process and progress are to be made at the district level, at least twice a year, and appropriate instructions are to be given.

In those schools where more number of children are outside the mainstream of learning, special attention is to be given and progress is to be followed.

Private and aided private schools, which did not show keen interest in the Mission activities, should take up this issue seriously. The Department may have to address them suitably, as the problem does not limit itself only to government schools.

There must be all-out efforts to reduce disability of children to reach the expected level of learning.

Department of Education should fill vacant posts of teachers so as to enable the schools to do important academic works including those connected with the issue of FLN.

CONCLUSION:

Foundational Literacy and Numeracy amongst children during early schooling acts as a foundation to future education and subsequent wellbeing as adults.

Learning disability among children, especially at the early schooling is assuming serious proportion as a hindrance to education among children across the states including Karnataka. Various state, national, world reports confirm this. If left unaddressed, there can be a negative impact of the issue of FLN on the human resource development of the country/state/district.

There is an immediate need to work out strategies to check this malady, especially in the rural schools.

FLN Abhiyan conceived, designed and executed by the Department of Education (with DIET) in Udupi district is a novel project which has yielded good dividends. The officials of the department and many teachers at various schools (mainly government schools) have given their best to make the Abhiyan a success.

Now, the idea should be institutionalised on a priority basis.

Certain of the important suggestions given as an output of the study may be considered for implementation. Certain policies need be created to address the issue effectively.

REFERENCES:

Annual National Education Report(1990-91), Department of EDUCATION/Ministry of Human Resource Development, New Delhi.

Annual Status of Education Report, (2006)Pratham Resource Centre , Mumbai, India.

Constitution of India(1950), Forty Second Amendment to Constitution,Ministry of Parlimentary AFFAIRS, government of India, New Delhi.

Krishna Kothaiand Ashok Kamath(2024), Problems of Early Childhood Education amongst Children of Migrant Labourers-A Study in Udupi District-Karnataka,Poornaprajna Journal, Udupi.

National Literacy Mission, Ministry of Human Resource Development, New Delhi.

Malgavkar P. D,(1995), Bihar Education Project, Rajasthan'sLokJumbish, Uttara Pradesh's Education for All,

Centre for Policy Research,Konark Publishers Pvt.Ltd. Delhi.

Srinivasa Bharath M.M.(2024),Story of the Brain for Youngsters, Navakarnataka Publication Pvt.Ltd., Bangalore.

Ramakrishna Bhat Chokkady(2025),Efforts to improve the degraded quality of Education,Udayavani, Manipal.

Udupi District Human Development Report-2008, Planning, Programme Monitoring and Statistics Department, Government of Karnataka, Multistoreyed Building, Bangalore.

International Literacy Year(1990), United Nation's Development Programme, UNDP Office, New Delhi.

World Bank Progress Report(2023), Washington D.C.

ಈ ಕೆಳಗಿನವುಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಗಣಿಸಿ

ವಿವರ	ತರಗತಿ									TOT AL
	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
ಎಫ್.ಎಲ್.ಎನ್. ಸಾಧಿಸಿದವರು	107	110	128	125	126	121	138	135	133	1125
ಎಫ್.ಎಲ್.ಎನ್. ಸಾಧಿಸದೇ ಇರುವವರು	58	14	22	30	14	05	39	15	18	15
ಎಫ್.ಎಲ್.ಎನ್. ಸಾಧಿಸದೇ ಇರುವವರು	134	143	161	162	174	156	161	146	130	1369
ಒಟ್ಟು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು	2	5	1	5	2	1	5	2	2	5
Classwise Average	121	124	144	141	143	136	154	149	146	1262
	00	49	33	55	56	66	54	77	20	10
	11.	11.	11.	11.	12.	11.	10.	9.7	8.9	10.8
	09	53	16	48	13	42	45	6	1	5
ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಶಾಲೆಗಳ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು	447	477	536	534	511	455	482	464	503	4414
ಎಫ್.ಎಲ್.ಎನ್. ಸಾಧಿಸದೇ ಇರುವವರು	8	3	4	8	2	3	9	7	6	0
	654	731	806	826	856	731	795	729	582	6710

ಬುನಾದಿ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯ ಖಾತ್ರಿಪಡಿಸಿದ ಶಾಲೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಅಭಿನಂದನ ಪತ್ರ ವಿತರಣೆ

ಉಡುಪಿ, ಮಾ.15: ಜಿಲ್ಲಾ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಮತ್ತು ತರಬೇತಿ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆ (ಡಯಟ್), ನಿರ್ವಹಣಾ ಭಾರತ್ ಮಿಷನ್ ವತಿಯಿಂದ ಶುಕ್ರವಾರ ಜಿಲ್ಲಾಧಿಕಾರಿ ಕಚೇರಿ ಸಂಕೀರ್ಣದ ಆಟಲ್ ಬಿಹಾರಿ ವಾಜಪೇಯಿ ಸಭಾಂಗಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಹಮ್ಮಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದ ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮದಲ್ಲಿ ಜಿಲ್ಲಾಧಿಕಾರಿ ಡಾ|| ಕೆ. ವಿದ್ಯಾಕುಮಾರಿ, ಜಿ.ಪಂ. ಸಿಇಒ ಪ್ರತಿಕ್ ಬಾಯಲ್ ಅವರು 'ಬುನಾದಿ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯ ಖಾತ್ರಿ ಪಡಿಸಿದ ಶಾಲೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಅಭಿನಂದನ ಪತ್ರ' ವಿತರಿಸಿದರು. ಅನಂತರ ಮಾತನಾಡಿದ ಡಿ.ಪಿ. ಪ್ರತಿಕ್ ಮಗುವಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಇರುವ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯವನ್ನು

ಗುರುತಿಸಿ ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹಿಸ ಬೇಕು. ಹೆತ್ತವರು ಅನಕ್ಷರಸ್ವರಾಗಿದ್ದಲ್ಲಿ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರ ಕಾರ್ಯ ಇನ್ನಷ್ಟು ಬದ್ಧತೆಯಿಂದ ಕೂಡಿರಬೇಕು. ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದಿನಿತೂ ಕೀಳರಿಮೆ ಮೂಡದಂತೆ ಎಚ್ಚರಿಕೆಯಿಂದ ಕರ್ತವ್ಯ ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸಬೇಕು. ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗೆ ಪ್ರಾಥಮಿಕ ಹಂತದಲ್ಲಿ ಬುನಾದಿಯನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸಿದ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರೇ ಆದರ್ಶವಾಗಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಎಂದರು. ಡಯಟ್ ಪ್ರಾಂಶುಪಾಲ ಗೋವಿಂದ ಮಡಿವಾಳ ಉಪಸ್ಥಿತರಿದ್ದರು. 93 ಶಾಲೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಪ್ರಶಸ್ತಿ ಪತ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ಪುಸ್ತಕ ಸ್ಮರಣಿಕೆ ನೀಡಿ ಗೌರವಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಯ 570 ಸರಕಾರ

ಪ್ರಾಥಮಿಕ ಶಾಲೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ 82 ಪ್ರಾಥಮಿಕ ಶಾಲೆಗಳು ಈ ಪ್ರಶಸ್ತಿಗೆ ಭಾಜನರಾದವು. ಇದಲ್ಲದೇ 6 ಅನುದಾನಿತ ಮತ್ತು 5 ಅನುದಾನರಹಿತ ಶಾಲೆಗಳು ಪ್ರಶಸ್ತಿ ಪಡೆದವು. ಪ್ರತಿಕ್ ವಲಯದ ಎಫ್.ಎಲ್.ಎನ್ ನೋಡಲ್ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿ ಬಿಆರ್.ಪಿ.ಎಸ್.ಪ್ರಶಸ್ತಿ ನೀಡಲಾಯಿತು. ಡಯಟ್‌ನ ಹಿರಿಯ ಉಪನ್ಯಾಸಕ ಡಾ|| ಅಶೋಕ್ ಕಾಮತ್ ಸ್ವಾಗತಿಸಿ, ಪ್ರಾಸ್ತಾವನೆಯನ್ನಿತ್ತರು. ಹಿರಿಯ ಉಪನ್ಯಾಸಕ ರಾಜಪ್ರಭಾಕರಮಿತ್ರಾಂತ್, ಸುಬ್ರಹ್ಮಣ್ಯಪ್ರಶಸ್ತಿ ಪುರಸ್ಕೃತ ಶಾಲೆಗಳ ಪಟ್ಟಿ ವಾಚಿಸಿದರು.

